

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_natural_d_Topo		
Created on:	4/13/2021 1:29:35 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	45.01	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.6868	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...x_natural_d_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/13/2021 1:29:35 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	14.43	μm	
Min:	-8.671	μm	
Max:	5.763	μm	
Size:	210177	digits	
Spacing:	0.06868	nm	
NM-points ratio:	64.70 % (5822614 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/13/2021 1:29:35 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis: X			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Y			
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis: Z			
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	14.43	μm	
Size:	210177	digits	
Spacing:	0.06868	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	1.992	μm	
Ssk	-0.5389		
Sku	3.594		
Sp	5.621	μm	
Sv	8.814	μm	
Sz	14.43	μm	
Sa	1.574	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	0.1832	%	
Smc	2.450	μm	
Sxp	4.445	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	18.07	μm	
Str	0.8473		
Std	176.3	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.6083		
Sdr	14.06	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.06671	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vv	2.517	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmp	0.06671	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vmc	1.809	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvc	2.247	μm ³ /μm ²	
Vvv	0.2695	μm ³ /μm ²	

Analyses:

ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	9.565	µm
Mean depth of furrows	2.515	µm
Mean density of furrows	4348	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	0.01162	°
Second direction	44.98	°
Third direction	90.01	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	82.74	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

